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The LUNZ Hub's RESPECT Project

The interdisciplinary Rapid Engagement with Stressed Peatland Environments and Communities in Transformation (RESPECT) project is affiliated with the Land Use for Net Zero, Nature and People (LUNZ) Hub and is funded by the UKRI Land Use for Net Zero programme. RESPECT aims to produce data, methods, landholder tools and proposals for governance reforms to change agricultural practices on peatland. RESPECT brings together researchers across Scotland and England with expertise in the natural and social sciences, humanities and law. RESPECT will also produce the Peatland Triage Tool (PTT), providing decision-support for landowners, land managers, farmers and crofters (collectively 'landholders') seeking to undertake peatland restoration. Upon completion, RESPECT will be able to provide a solid evidence base, and tools to inform land use decisions in relation to the restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands.

This response was drafted with input from across our interdisciplinary RESPECT Team.

RESPECT response to the Environment and Climate Change Committee's call for evidence on England's drought preparedness

This inquiry will focus on drought management practices and policies and consider whether these are sufficient for responding to current and future droughts. The inquiry will cover impacts, monitoring, engagement and changes in supply and demand, aiming to identify opportunities for improved drought preparedness and response in England.

Introduction

Dr Barratt and Prof Whitehouse are based at the University of Glasgow, Archaeology, School of Humanities. Dr Barratt is a Research Associate on the RESPECT project and Prof Whitehouse is a Prof of Archaeological Science and Co-I on the project. They are experts in peatland environments, in their various facets, including their historic environment and their palaeoecology. Dr Bunting is based at the University of Hull, Geography and Environment, School of Environmental and Life Sciences, also a Co-I on the RESPECT project. She is a long-term ecologist with research interests focused on better understanding of the long-term ecological dynamics of cultural landscapes. She also has considerable expertise in peatlands.

The "Rapid Engagement with Stressed Peatland Environments and Communities in Transformation (RESPECT)" project is affiliated with the Land Use for Net Zero, Nature and People (LUNZ) Hub and is funded by the UKRI's (BBSRC) Land Use for Net Zero programme. RESPECT aims to produce data, methods, landholder tools and proposals for governance reforms to change agricultural practices on peatland. Upon completion, RESPECT will be able to provide a solid evidence base, and tools to inform land use decisions in relation to the restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands. More information on the project may be found here: <https://lunzhub.com/projects/respect/>

Rationale

We are submitting evidence because increased drought has considerable implications for peatlands and their vital ecosystem services, including social well-being, climate mitigation, biodiversity, water management and the economy. Peatlands are wetland ecosystems where drought will have considerable impacts. They are likely to be uniquely vulnerable to increased drought conditions. Our written submission addresses questions 1, 2 and 10.

1. What are the potential risks of increased drought in England to: the urban, industrial, and rural environment; people, species and habitats; and the economy?

We comment on the specific case of peatlands: unique habitats providing a host of short and long-term services to society, economy and culture. Peatlands are primarily a wetland ecosystem, dependent upon a delicate hydrological balance to maintain their viability and very existence. A functioning peatland can serve to mitigate floods, capture and store carbon for millennia, preserve our nations' heritage, enhance biodiversity and are an important supply of high-quality drinking water for England [1,2]. Though many of the UK's peatlands have been damaged and degraded, active intervention is providing a means for recovery. Though this is a long-term process, benefits can be realised in years and can continue to accrue for centuries; for example, a damaged, drained and exploited peatland can be an active carbon source, but restoration of the hydrology and the surface vegetation can convert it into an active carbon sink, contributing to climate change mitigation whilst also improving water storage, reducing flood risk and supporting rich biodiversity and providing attractive and interesting habitats for human recreation. Increased drought frequency and duration pose a significant threat to currently functioning peatlands and to already damaged sites, accelerating the rate of breakdown and carbon release, since damaged sites have low resilience to external changes [3,4]. Drought will therefore increase economic costs due of damaged peatlands (e.g. lack of natural flood protection) and the cost and difficulty of any future restoration of damaged sites, leading to impacts on future societal wellbeing, ecological diversity and the economy.

Increased drought will also impact the biodiversity of many peatlands, including specialist species that rely upon ombrotrophic (acid) conditions such as specialist lower plants (e.g. Sphagnum moss, Drosera spp. Sundews, Bog Aspodel, Bog rosemary) and insects that rely upon these habitats (e.g. acidophilous water beetles and ground beetles) and reduce both open water habitats and the water retention characteristics of many of our peatlands. Both characteristics play an important part of up-stream water management of catchment systems which protect our urban centres from down-stream flooding. Increased drought is also likely to make peatlands more vulnerable to natural burning, releasing old carbon trapped within peatlands and compromising the habitat quality of extant peatlands and their ongoing restoration efforts.

Drought will compromise the preservation of waterlogged archaeological sites and the wider historic environment preserved within peatlands, through the process of drying. This leads to degradation of waterlogged materials and their eventual disappearance. The types of sites that may be impacted by drought include wooden structures (e.g. trackways; occupation sites) and artefacts and other organic materials such as wood, fabric, leather, baskets and rope, plant remains, tablets, human remains (e.g. bog bodies). Drought is already impacting archaeological sites and associated peat deposits; a good example is the important Roman fort of Vindolanda, which is now suffering from considerable drying and degradation of its waterlogged peatrich deposits [5]. Drought will impact all waterlogged archaeological deposits, whether in peatlands or not, including from deep urban contexts, or from wetland contexts in rural dryland sites and landscapes and so is of considerable concern to the archaeological community. This will impact the rich heritage of the British people, affecting social well-being but also the economy.

Archaeology is a place-based discipline dedicated to helping people understand and shape the places and communities in which they live, work and play. Our landscapes, whether urban or rural, coastal, marine or upland, have all been shaped by past human activity over thousands of years. Archaeology employs thousands of people directly, making it a bigger UK industry than marine fishing. It forms a crucial part of the heritage sector, contributing billions annually to the economy as part of tourism, construction and many allied areas (CBA Archaeology Enriches us all Promotional Leaflet).

2. How will climate change affect drought risk (including severity, frequency and type) and impacts of drought?

England's winters are getting wetter, but the summers are becoming warmer [6]. Increased summer temperatures lead to greater evapotranspiration, water usage and abstraction. In addition, an increase in extreme events such as prolonged drought is expected [7]. Winter precipitation is not always sufficient to offset summer calls on our water resources and a dry winter can lead to multi-year deficits [8]. Peatlands are

particularly susceptible to devastating fires under these conditions. Such conflagrations, enhanced by climate change, can release centuries worth of sequestered carbon, destroy or severely damage England's irreplaceable Historic Environment, and devastate habitats and biodiversity for years or decades [9]. Drought induced by climate change is likely to increase in severity under a range of increasingly probable global temperature projections [10]. In this context, increasing occurrences of peatland fires are likely, contributing to further global warming and diminishing England's water storage capacity, reducing drought resilience.

10. How should the Government consider drought management alongside its other priorities such as nature restoration, food security, flood management and expansion of artificial intelligence?

Management of peatlands to improve drought resilience and to protect functions during droughts should be considered part of the toolkit available to address other important priorities such as nature restoration, flood management and climate change mitigation. Poor drought management leading to changes in peatland water table levels can significantly affect the ecosystem services they provide. Drought lowers water levels, increasing the oxygen availability in the drained peat and shifting the system from storing to releasing carbon, affecting climate mitigation. The rate of carbon loss due to even a short-term drought event can be the equivalent of decades of sequestration [11]. Even short-term drying events lasting a few days can alter ecological processes and cause stress and damage to species, since rewetting and restoration of peatland function can take multiple weeks [12]. Repeated drying events can lead to breakdown of the peat structure, reducing its water holding capacity and therefore degrading its ability to mitigate future flood events. Lowered water levels and increased oxygen in exposed peat also increases the rate of loss of the historic environment record preserved in the peat [13]. Millennia of evidence of human culture, climate and landscape change are at risk of being damaged or permanently lost.

Increased drought in England, whether short or prolonged in length, will not only have real impact on carbon budgets and the historic environment but also puts at risk significant investments into restoration of peatlands if the sites being restored have not sufficiently recovered to have natural resilience in face of a particular event. Management of peatlands to increase their resilience to drought events, whether by maintaining the function of current healthy sites or by improving and restoring damaged sites, is both a direct drought management action and makes an active contribution to delivering on other commitments such as flood risk management, climate change mitigation, biodiversity recovery and protection of the historic environment.

References

- [1] Hazell, Z. et al. (2022) 'Peatlands and the historic environment in England – working together to make the difference', *Journal of Wetland Archaeology*, 22(1–2), pp. 160–171. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14732971.2023.2211739>.
- [2] Defra (2021) *England Peat Action Plan*. London: UK Government.
- [3] Ritson, J.P. et al. (2025) 'Climate change impacts on blanket peatland in Great Britain', *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 62(3), pp. 701–714. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14864>.
- [4] Swindles, G.T. et al. (2019) 'Widespread drying of European peatlands in recent centuries', *Nature Geoscience*, 12(11), pp. 922–928. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-019-0462-z>
- [5] Taylor, G. et al. (2025) *Characterising the degradation of leather through the decades: Evidence from 50 years of excavations at Vindolanda Roman fort*. Proceedings of the 16th Conference of the ICOM-CC wet organic archaeological materials working group, Gothenburg, 2025. Available at: <https://www.icomccpublications-online.org/6995/Characterising-the-degradation-of-leather-through-the-decades-Evidencefrom-50-years-of-excavations-at-Vindolanda-Roman-fort>
- [6] Kendon, M. et al. (2025). 'State of the UK Climate in 2024.' *International Journal of Climatology* 45, no. S1: e70010. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.70010>.

- [7] Chan, W.C.H., Arnell, N.W., Darch, G., Facer-Childs, K., Shepherd, T.G., Tanguy, M., van der Wiel, K. (2023). 'Current and future risk of unprecedented hydrological droughts in Great Britain', *Journal of Hydrology*, 625A, 130074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2023.130074> .
- [8] Environment Agency (2025) 5. Environment - drought risks, impacts and actions: Drought prospects for spring 2026, GOV.UK. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/drought-prospects-for-spring-2026/5-environment-drought-risks-impacts-and-actions-drought-prospects-for-spring-2026> (Accessed: 18 November 2025).
- [9] Baker, S.J. et al. (2025) 'Spikes in UK wildfire emissions driven by peatland fires in dry years', *Environmental Research Letters*, 20(3), p. 034028. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1088/17489326/adafc6>.
- [10] Hanlon, H.M. et al. (2021) 'Future changes to high impact weather in the UK', *Climatic Change*, 166(3), p. 50. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-021-03100-5>.
- [11] Quan, Q. et al. (2025) 'Drought-induced peatland carbon loss exacerbated by elevated CO2 and warming', *Science*, 390(6771), pp. 367–370. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adv7104>.
- [12] Keane, B. et al. (2025) 'The effects of drought on Sphagnum moss species and the implications for hydrology in peatlands', *New Phytologist*, 247(5), pp. 2003–2021. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.70361>.
- [13] Matthiesen, H. et al. (2022) 'Wetland archaeology and the impact of climate change', *Antiquity*, 96(390), pp. 1412–1426. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15184/aqy.2022.112>.